

Welcome to the qualitative survey on the use and further development of persistent identifiers (PIDs) in Germany.

Thank you for your interest and for taking the time to participate in this survey.

As part of the DFG-funded research project “PID Network Germany,” [506475377](#), on the current and future use of persistent identifiers in Germany, we would like to engage in dialogue with you, stakeholders from PID registration agencies, aggregators, citation databases, and infrastructure initiatives, through this online survey. This survey aims to gain a well-founded understanding of the current status, your existing needs, supply gaps, and development potential in addressing PIDs.

Participation is voluntary.

The following questions serve as a guide. Free text fields allow you to describe your experiences and perspectives in detail. There are no “right” or “wrong” answers—your individual perspective is particularly valuable to us.

We would be delighted to publish your answers as a PDF document, along with the evaluation, on [Zenodo.org](#).

No participation

For publishing:

Consent

No consent

Anonymous

With name, ORCID iD if applicable

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Organization/Institution: DataCite - DOI Agency

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If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact me, Andreas Czerniak (andreas.czerniak@uni-bielefeld.de), at any time. In addition, we, the PID Network Project Team (info.pidnetwork@listserv.dfn.de), will be happy to assist you with any questions you may have regarding PIDs, both in a national and international context.

I'm immensely grateful for your assistance.

1. Status Quo and Utilization

A guiding question in this section could be:

- How is your infrastructure or service currently being used, and what typical usage scenarios or use cases can be identified?

DataCite infrastructure and services are currently used by 1700+ member organizations, dozens of service provider platforms and harvesting services, and numerous other users worldwide.

Infrastructure and service usage encompasses DOI registration, metadata management, metadata retrieval and analysis, and metadata harvesting.

Typical use cases for DataCite infrastructure and services include registering DOIs, enabling discoverability and visibility of research outputs and activities, analyzing research outputs and activities, tracking citations, and retrieving and harvesting metadata.

2. Infrastructure and Services

Some guiding questions in this section could be:

- In your opinion, which research infrastructures and services are particularly relevant for the operation and further development of PIDs for your service?
- For which external services or infrastructures does your service currently provide essential functionalities or interfaces, and in what form does this take place? What role do PIDs play in this?
- Do you use PIDs to operate your service?

DataCite is a DOI Registration Agency and supports registration of DOIs. The DataCite Metadata Schema supports numerous other persistent identifiers, such as ROR IDs for organizations and ORCID iDs for creators and contributors.

DataCite DOIs are a crucial part of the research ecosystem and are relied upon by numerous organizations, services, and other users worldwide to make research more

open and discoverable and to retrieve, analyze, or otherwise consume information about research.

3. Needs and Wishes

Some guiding questions in this section could be:

- In your opinion, what specific developments or changes would be beneficial to maximize the potential of PIDs better?
- What structural, technical, or political measures would be necessary to boost the expansion of PID infrastructures in Germany specifically?

The primary development or change that would help to maximize the potential of PIDs is broad and effective adoption of a core set of widely recognized global PIDs associated with the core building blocks of the research information ecosystem.

A secondary development or change would be rich and usable metadata associated with PIDs that aids in discovery, disambiguation, and reporting precision.

Additional developments or changes could involve resourcing and capacity-building to support widespread adoption and implementation of best practices.

To boost the adoption of PIDs at research institutions in Germany, a coordinated approach must consider the country's federal political system. A national PID strategy involving relevant stakeholders is a necessary top-down step to complement ongoing bottom-up integration and awareness-raising efforts.

4. Recommendations

Some guiding questions in this section could be:

- Which actors (e.g., research infrastructures, scientific societies/communities, funding organizations, libraries) do you believe are responsible for enabling more effective use of PIDs, and what tasks should each of them take on?
- Which additional aspects do you consider relevant, and what recommendations would you give us concerning taking them into account?

Since several other countries have successfully developed national PID strategies, it would be worthwhile consulting the relevant organizations to find out what challenges they encountered during the process.